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STUDY ON THE IT INDUSTRY OF HYDERABAD CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND POSSIBLE WAYS AHEAD

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ABSTRACT

Hyderabad's trajectory of growth to its present-day status of being one of the world's leading IT-Hub has been in the making for at least the last three decades. This study breaks down this growth into three distinct parts. Firstly, the study explores the data and bring out any overt and covert models that were followed. Insights from ethnographic interviews of ex-bureaucrats and I.T. businesses were used to explicate these models. Second, using primary and secondary data, a part of the study also looks into the start-up ecosystem that presently exists in and around Hyderabad. Third, from secondary data, the also tries to understand the international trade in I.T. and I.T. services. The study also looks at understanding the future readiness of the city by getting insights from I.T. Industry's business leaders.

A SHORT BRIEF ABOUT THE PROJECT AND THE SPEAKERS SO FAR

If one were to look back at understanding Hyderabad's trajectory to being an I.T. Hub, it is hard to locate literature that has been concertedely created detailing this story and history. There is press coverage, academic research and other literature of issues disjointly, but we were not able to find a body of knowledge that compositely told the story of Hyderabad's I.T. trajectory.

This project was conceived to explore the metamorphosis and what-went-right in the transformation of a city of pearls and the twin-cities to that of a global I.T. Hub.

Data collection for the project started off with interviewing bureaucrats that held-fort in the early to mid-1990's. Hyderabad's transformation to an IT-Hub largely started in the mid 1990's. This said, the mid 1990's was only the tipping point. To be able to arrive at this tipping point, work on the city's abilities and offerings have divergently evolved over the two or three decades preceding the nineties.

One striking point that comes across as a part of this exercise is what is considered a daily reality in most of the global north, 'decentralisation of governance'.

THE HISTORIES AND NARRATIVES OF THE I.T. INDUSTRY OF HYDERABAD

Section 1 is based on ethnographic narratives and observations made from interviewing ex-bureaucrats and I.T. businesses. We try to present here, an ethnographic record of Hyderabad's I.T. journey. Narratives from Historians, cultural experts, geographers have also been included in the study.

SECTION - 1

1.1 A SNAPSHOT OF HYDERABAD'S I.T. JOURNEY

1.1.1 The erstwhile state of Hyderabad and its forethought for the Industry of its day

Right from embracing the railroad and telegram/telegraph in the Mid-19th century to a possibly the first in the world consolidated transport management (Air/Rail/Road), Hyderabad's ability to surf the technology wave for the last couple of centuries has always had it at the fore.

Looking inward for growth

With no ports, Hyderabad was landlocked. The growth of Hyderabad as an industrial space had to be garnered and built from within the city. By the 1900s, other parts of the country then were decades ahead in setting up their industries, not just port cities, but other landlocked cities like Kanpur with its multiple textile mills. Hyderabad set up its first Karkhana (Meaning 'factory' in Dakhani Language) in 1916 in the Hussaini Alam area. The Nizam of the time, Mir Osman Ali Khan, decided to set up a button-making factory. The logic being the fact that the city was populated with Sherwani wearing elites who would need buttons to suit-up. So began the Deccan Button Factory, which are collectors' items to this day, says one of our interlocutors who is a historian, cultural ambassador and proudly calls herself a Mulki (Born citizen of the erstwhile Hyderabad State). Hyderabad not being a port city hindered its economic growth pace; it did have other resources though.

Nonetheless, in the form of coal and cotton, Hyderabad had the raw material needed for the Industry of the late 19th and the early 20th century. To be able to send coal out from the Godavari valley, a railway line came up.

In a couple of decades following 1910, there was a push from the Nizams to industrialise the city of Hyderabad. The creation of The Industrial Trust fund, equivalent to today's Telangana Industries Department, happened then, and it began setting up small and medium-sized factories. Hyderabad then saw the emergence of industries such as the Charminar Cigarettes factory, the Golconda cigarettes factory, Deccan Glass factory, Allaudin company making sheet metal, which slowly started transitioning to making metal bodies of public buses etc. The effort to spring up the industrial movement in Hyderabad was expressly seen and felt, but it was not as much as other cities.

Pre- I.T. industry evolution, politics, people and spaces

In the 1960s, with the dominance of the public sector undertakings, heavy industry emerged prominently in Hyderabad and Bangalore.

Chronicling the change in Hyderabad since the 1960s

The advent of the 60s in Hyderabad brought about some changes to its existing industry sector. Drawing parallels between Hyderabad and Bangalore, both were land-locked and politically important, they started to push for public sector undertakings (PSUs). At the same time that the industrial impetuous came up in Hyderabad, a big push for the agriculture sector was ongoing in the 60s. The green revolution ushered in, and dams were being built. All around Hyderabad, factories like BHEL (Bharat Heavy Electricals Ltd), HMT(Hindustan Machine Tools), HAL (Hindustan Aeronautical Ltd), ECIL (Electronics Corporation of India) started propping up.

The Defence sector set up DRDL (Defence Research and Development Laboratory) and DRDO (Defence Research and Development Organisation); the pharmaceuticals sector saw IDPL (Indian Drugs and Pharmaceuticals) being set up. These PSUs came up by taking up vast amounts of land, and this is where the city's blue- and white-collar employment belonged. In the years to come, the advent of this new change in propping of the new Industry provided the necessary linkages for the story of the city's transportation, its housing and the jobs it would then see.

Patterns of work and mobility in Hyderabad

During the 1960s and 70s, you there were three kinds of movements largely visible in the city. One set of people travelled to the city centre for work, where the secretariat was situated. The other set of people went to the Charminar area for an informal type of work. And the third travelled to the northwest side (Lingampally, Patancheru, Chanda Nagar, Sanath Nagar, etc.) or slightly towards the northeast of Hyderabad towards ECIL for factory-based work. Factory workers used to travel in factory buses in shifts, and Hyderabad had a system similar to that of the Dabbawallas (of Mumbai). Lunches would be picked up on bicycles and delivered at the factory to the workers. These were the pattern of jobs, transportation, and mobility pattern in the 60s and 70s in Hyderabad.

The 1970s began to see a shift in the work and mobility patterns in the city. The beneficiaries of the agricultural surplus created from the regions of coastal Andhra were looking for avenues of investment. They were looking for urban centres to invest in; Vizag and the other Hyderabad had a couple of options. Hyderabad was going through an unstable environment where the city was fraught with its political situation. The agitation for a separate state of Telangana was bubbling up in the late 1960s, mainly with employment and education issues. The uncertainty and turmoil persisted through the 70s; only in the 1980s, Hyderabad saw some assertive political changes.

1.2 (THE 1970s) THE COMPUTING INDUSTRY

All around the world, microprocessor-based computing systems were in their evolutionary phases, and so was the case in India. The hardware systems were clunky and large; the size of a computer and its storage almost filled a room, which today is a quarter of the size of what our smartphones can hold. There were no P.C.s or intelligent systems, only 2nd and 3rd generation (Stallings, 2016) systems built with logical circuits. In those days analogue computers were used to develop mini systems. The computer systems in the 70s were not indigenous; they were imported until Electronics Corporation of India Limited (ECIL) started manufacturing its own in the 80s.

In the 70s, India had a strained relationship with the U.S. Therefore, India made a pact with Russia (then USSR) to import hardware. Russia made a replica of the computer system IBM360 and sold it to India. In return, India developed and exported software to the Russians. However, the mainframe's quality was subpar; the machines were so humungous in size, cranes were used to transport and install these systems.

Electronics Corporation of India Limited (ECIL) was set up in Hyderabad by the Bhabha Atomic Research Centre (BARC). ECIL had started manufacturing the hardware of computer systems such as TDC12, TDC312, TDC316 (Narasimhan & P V S Rao, 1984). They mainly catered to Defence and Nuclear areas and projects where these computers were integrated for use. Hyderabad and

the I.T. sector were fortunate to have an organisation like ECIL catering to a computer system's hardware element in the city. The establishment of ECIL created a pool of talent in the electronics and computers field in the Hyderabad region. ECIL has played a pivotal role, especially in training. "Even a diploma holder became an expert in design and development" – that was the kind of training given at ECIL.

The late 70s and the 80s saw the advent of smaller software companies come to life. In its nascent stages, the Industry saw professionals from the public sector slowly shifting to the private sector.

In the era of license raj, the Indian economy was closed off to the world and draconian restrictions international trade made it challenge to be in the technology business. Government regulation regarding import and export created barriers were like no other. All movement and processes by industries were monitored strictly by the government.

Every activity by software companies required permissions for any export, travelling to the U.S., opening a bank account in the U.S., etc. Tedious processes and strict regulation stifled the process of growth. Software companies at the time, especially small-scale ones, found it hard to survive unless they were a niche market. The market already had the prominent Tata Consultancy Services (TCS) to manufacture systems' mainframe. The government had a tight leash on the software companies; they had to report each rupee spent and earned monthly and quarterly reports. Submit all their invoices and receipts to the RBI (Reserve Bank of India), failing which the companies were legally liable.

"There was a lack of knowledge and openness by the bureaucrats who knew close to nothing about technology. The lack of freedom and support by authorities made it a difficult place to do technology business." - Mr. Rentala Chandrashekar

1.3 (THE 1980s) THE BEGINNING OF P.C. USE, NETWORKING, BRAIN DRAIN AND THE SPURT OF THE I.T. CRAZE

P.C. usage hugely increased due to its affordability. Digital communication and networking began in the 80s with a slow network. Thus, was started for educational purposes with the introduction of The Education and Research Network (ERNET) and subsequently National Informatics Centre Network (NICNET) (Wolcot & Goodman, 2003) Unix (computer operating system) based machines were manufactured by ECIL, which became popular with P.C.s.

Many new languages and web-based applications started to develop during this decade. The 80s also saw the rise and fall of many companies. Companies from the U.S. which were at the top of their game could not sustain post that decade. To name a few, Univar and Digital were competitors to IBM, but they do not exist today. Due to the rapid growth and competition, they sold off their companies to others and were absorbed. By the end of the decade, ECIL became the leading local manufacturer in mini and super-minicomputers.

1.3.1 Hyderabad's Transnational connections and its transition to the global village

Interesting connections began to take place in Hyderabad. Two distinct transnational connections emerged; the first was between Hyderabad and the Middle East. New labour markets were opening up in large numbers. Demand and pull were such that persons with existing jobs would go on for 1–2-year leaves without pay and move to the Middle East to work for a few years and

move back. The second connection was with the United States of America. Young people moved to the U.S. post their school and college education, particularly in medicine and engineering.

Those migrating, especially to the U.S., had some connections to Vengalrao Nagar and Ameerpet (both areas in Hyderabad city). Most emigrating persons belonged to these areas; social networks' operation can be observed with this pattern. People who lived in these areas were primarily blue/white-collar employees of the industries set up in the 70s-80s or ones that had agricultural surpluses from the Andhra areas and settled in Hyderabad. They built homes in these areas, as this area was then the city's outskirts.

Children of these first generation white- and blue-collar workers were the first I.T. engineers that emigrated to the global north. When Hyderabad started beaconing to be an I.T. services hub, the people networks of these young emigrant I.T. workers from the Ameerpet area played a significant role in the early 90s to bring back work to the city as an offshore work haven. A good example is Satya Nadella and the Microsoft Development centre coming up in Hyderabad.

1.4 (THE 1990s) TRANSITIONING FROM THE LICENSE RAJ TO A GLOBAL I.T. HUB:

1.4.1 Economic reforms, I.T. industry's changing trajectories, political will, government dynamism.

The 90s Liberalisation-Privatisation-Globalisation (LPG) economic reforms had kicked into motion. Ushered in by the LPG, there was an economic surplus, and consumer spending started increasing. Products such as refrigerators, motor vehicles, telephones, television, etc., started to have a market, and Hyderabad began producing them. ECIL made television sets, Allwyn produced refrigerators, watches, scooters (Pushpak), etc. Along with these new markets for a range of consumer durable goods manufactured in the city, commercial markets were also budding during the 90s. Businesses ventures like ploy clinics, tutorial colleges started propping up in some areas of the city.

1.4.2 United Streets of Ameerpet

Software Technology Park of India (STPI) was setup during the early 90s. It brought commercial internet access, enabling global I.T. Business, with which the offshore work model began coming into the city. The Southern regional headquarters for STPI was set up at Maitrivanam in Ameerpet. It made Maitrivanam an anchor point for I.T. and I.T. enabled services. It was from here that these services from Hyderabad were exported to other parts of the world. Soon, progressing from offering offshore services, STPI-Maitrivanam in Ameerpet also became a centre from where I.T. personnel were also sent to work abroad. Back in the day, this model was called 'body-shopping'.

Biao's book – "Global Body Shopping: An Indian Labor System in the Information Technology Industry", precisely talks about this (Biao, 2007). Biao points to a large number of graduate children of affluent or dominant-caste, land-owning people of coastal Andhra having a foot in Ameerpet in a hope to move to the U.S. as 'bodies' in the body-shopping trade, aided by H1B Visas. This movement and demand shift pattern could be seen and was possible due to a massive marketing job termed the 'Y2K problem'. Y2K problem meant that all dates in software created in the world until the mid-1990s worked in the two-digit year format MM-DD-YY or YY-DD-MM or

DD-YY-MM. All these dates created until then needed to be migrated to take in the 'four-digit year (XXXX)' before the year 2000 came in. Failing which, clocks of all computers would reset to year 00 (1900) instead of the year 2000. In case this change was not made, a digital Armageddon was forecasted.

"The Y2K crisis was partly because of clever marketing, partly because of the media role and hype, partly due to the then fledgeling Indian I.T. industry. Partly because of fact, the fear loomed across the world that all the computers could come crashing down on midnight of December 31, 1999."
- Mr. Rentala Chandrashekar

There started a desperate search for I.T. professionals, with skills that could help rewrite the code before the dawn of the new millennia. It was then that the world discovered India's I.T. industry. Hyderabad, in this scenario, had the most significant number of 'bodied workers who were sent across the globe for these I.T. services. Thus, Ameerpet became a funnel that sent out people to the U.S. in such massive numbers that it earned its nickname, "The United Streets of Ameerpet".

It became the hub for training centres. Maringanti describes Ameerpet as that destination where all types of I.T. related information and courses were to be found. The rarest of computer languages were taught in centres spread across streets. *"Ameerpet is a fantastic model for decentralised, informally organised self-created university establishment"* - Dr. Anant Maringanti.

1.5 (THE 2000s) Y2K CRISIS, THE EMPLOYMENT BOOM, RISE OF SOFTWARE HUB, HYDERABAD'S PIONEERING OF E-GOVERNANCE

1.5.1 The McKinsey Move

From the mid 90's the seed of the I.T. industry of Hyderabad can be traced back to one document, the Vision 2020. Tracing this document's origin leads us to McKinsey, a management consulting firm. It is interesting how this American firm manages to reach Hyderabad through a unique route. First landing up in Kuala Lumpur persuaded Mohamed Mahathir (Former PM of Malaysia) to build a cyber tower. Mc Kinsey then moved on to Calcutta to persuade Jyoti Basu (Former CM, West Bengal) to bring about changes in its economy and then to Chandra Babu Naidu (Former CM, Andhra Pradesh) to pursue the Vision of 2020. McKinsey convinced Naidu that there is a need for a Vision 2020 and reimagine how the economy should work. Furthermore, they convinced him about how Hyderabad would be a focal point of this I.T. growth.

"Andhra Pradesh will leverage I.T. to attain a position of leadership and excellence in the Information Age to transform itself into a Knowledge Society." (Sudan, 2000)

1.5.2 Going Global with I.T.

Before its branding as the global I.T. hub, Hyderabad was a blip on the world's radar. Consequently, the I.T. sector in the city required more than usual marketing effort. At Comdex, a computer expo trade show of the 90s and early 2000s, the realisation dawned on how much of an insignificant blip Hyderabad was on the global map. Questions that Sudan (I.T. Secretary-AP) and his team encountered at COMDEX were enquiring whether this Hyderabad was in Pakistan? Other such questions that arose were - 'Were there direct international flights available?'; 'Were there international schools open for the children of expatriates?'.

Selling India as an I.T. destination to the world was a mighty task. To sell the Indian I.T. industry, one had first to sell the whole idea of India. Eighty per cent of presentation pitches made to global investors explained India's potential, why India is the next big thing for I.T., why its computer industry was worth doing business with and then getting down to individual company abilities. The task of selling I.T. in India was dispersed across the Industry at that time.

The city was being pitched to global investors and companies left-right and centre as a destination they must visit and set up shop. However, Hyderabad lacked on various fronts. Availability and reliability of significant key infrastructure elements needed work.

Back in the day, there were terrible power shortages in Andhra Pradesh (united). There was no investment in power production for over ten years. Without having stable power, it was impossible to attract I.T. companies. Hyderabad had poor connectivity compared to the rest of the growing cities in this sector. Without infrastructure, global companies would not venture into Hyderabad; they would rather stay fleet-footed and occupy buildings on a rental basis. Smaller companies would not have the cost margins to invest in high infrastructure. Therefore, it came down to the government's role; it would be their job to create this infrastructure and the environment at a reasonable rate for companies to set up shop.

Although A.P. professionals are known for their I.T. skills, they were found more in Chennai or Bangalore than in Hyderabad. Hyderabad did not have good technical institutes unlike Chennai or Bangalore, the latter of which also had the prestigious Indian Institute of Science (IISc). There was a severe lack of quality educational institutions, both schools and higher education. Hyderabad and A.P. at the time also had restrictions that curtailed the social infrastructure. I.T. professionals worked long hours and needed to unwind at the end of the day to socialise and relax. The club and pub culture were still non-existent. Therefore, the question raised was, how was it expected to increase the quality workforce and then retain them without the said requirements?

The vision for Hyderabad in the 90s looked at an I.T.-B.T. (Information Technology-Biotechnology) hub. There was a movement to re-engineer the government, all its policies and functioning. Sheela Bhide describes the need to create and impress upon the private sector that the government was objective-driven and efficient, just like private companies. The government began a multi-pronged strategy to reduce expenditure on social welfare schemes and invest in power and infrastructure. The PPP (Public-Private Partnership) model was proposed for building roadways, power plants, etc. The airports were privatised, and Etihad was the first airline to come in, thanks to the middle east connection. Along with such investments, the prohibitions, and restrictions on social gatherings such as clubs and pubs eased. The government of A.P. started converting Hyderabad's drawbacks into its plus points.

1.5.3 Technical institutes of learning

Hyderabad did not have good quality technical institutes. Necessary training for I.T. personnel was not present in Hyderabad, and hence the local crowd spread out to other cities. In terms of workforce, A.P. was sitting on a pot of gold. The Indian School of Business (ISB) setting, currently in Hyderabad, was not its original destination. Mr Deepak Parekh, one of the industry insiders who wanted to set up the business school, pitched it to the Maharashtra government to be set up in

Mumbai. The pitch had its problems; the Maharashtra government raised some objections and conditions for setting up the school. The government demanded 20% of the seats be given local reservation to the state. While these negotiations were in the way, A.P. offered land and resources to set up the school. As a second option, The ISB considered and visited Hyderabad. Once they did, impressed with the openness and the support extended by the government, ISB decided to set up the school in Hyderabad.

1.5.4 The Bills and their Multiplier effects (Bill Gates & Bill Clinton's visit to Hyderabad)

It was 1997 when Bill Gates visited India and Hyderabad. But this was not to be the case. Gates was not scheduled to visit Hyderabad, but was persuaded with a short presentation. Gates appreciated the sincerity and clarity of thought and decided to send a team to assess the viability to set up Microsoft's development centre in Hyderabad.

The first team that visited Hyderabad went back unimpressed. Their visit to Chennai seemed successful, and hence the name recommended was Chennai. The government was unwilling to take this lightly and was keen to have Microsoft in Hyderabad. With all his NRI connections, including through Mr. Yugandhar, a senior IAS officer in Delhi whose son is Satya Nadella (present CEO/Chairman of Microsoft) and other networks, AP reached out to Gates and sought another chance. This time, Microsoft chose Hyderabad as their offshore development centre.

The next milestone was when Bill Clinton visited India in the 2000s. Clinton came with a barrage of top-class global companies and the international media with him. The government felt the need to direct Clinton's attention towards Hyderabad, which would give massive global mileage to the city. All efforts were made to bring Clinton to Hyderabad. The U.S. Ambassador was against it, as they had a tight schedule with no time to spare. With the continued persistence from the CM's office, the Ambassador obliged and invited the CM to join a private high-end dinner party hosted by him. A few moments alone with Clinton was what he promised the CM, which he got. Clinton was impressed, and the next time he visited India, he made sure to come to Hyderabad.

The visit was hosted at the Cyber towers, where the corridors were filled with guests and international media. The American media covered this and gave tremendous attention to Hyderabad globally.

Summarising this section, data from ethnographic interviews that were conducted support the popular idea that the push for the transformation of Hyderabad to an I.T. Hub has primarily been government-driven in the late 1990s and the early 2000s. Drawing up to the boom of the mid-1990s, the technological legacy of the pre-independent Hyderabad state, Hyderabad's geographical location, historical and demographic issues all came together. This coming together of the parts of the puzzle was a very concerted and conscious effort. Taking off from those foundations, the spirit of private entrepreneurship saw the Industry take to new heights.

SECTION - 2

2.1 THE START-UP CULTURE OF TELANGANA

2.1.1 Objective

Preliminary study on Telangana's start-up nature: An enquiry into how conducive and compatible Telangana state is for start-up growth.

This study aims to understand the start-up climate in Telangana and draws out the state's compatibility and conduciveness for I.T. start-up growth. In addition, the study examines start-up data to rank Telangana state's performance in the country.

2.1.2 Introduction

Innovation, creativity, and entrepreneurship are an essential milestone of the growing success of all developed nations. Start-ups and innovations have played a crucial role in transforming economies throughout the world. India has started a similar journey around the same time as the United Kingdom, making India a leading start-up hub. India aspires to become a \$5 Trillion economies by 2024. India wants to take advantage of its demographic dividend and convert it into high quality technical human resource by encouraging deep Tech entrepreneurship, research and innovation. The government of India first announced the Start-up action plan in 2016. India aspires to move its Global Innovation Index (GII) ranking within the top 25.

India has the advantage of an enormous vibrant market. 1 Billion plus population base, rising technology embracing entrepreneurs, pervasive tech innovation, growing middle class and simultaneous growth in consumption index, strong agriculture and industrial roots, high saving rate, increasing infrastructure and digital infrastructure, favourable regulatory (State) environment, falling cost of doing business, expanding investor group and next-generation technologies making India competitive and a hub for new generation Unicorns and Soonicorns. To add to India's achievements, it added 8 Unicorns in 2018 alone, and it is home to 26 Unicorns.

Celebrated start-ups in India are spread across various sectors: agriculture, health, logistics, Banking and Finance, Education, E-Commerce, Food, Insurance, Media, and Entertainment. Bookmyshow, Hotstar, Policybazaar, Paytm, Swiggy, Zomato, Licious, Flipkart, Nykaa, Byjus, Unacademy, Practo, Curefit, AgroStar, Ninjacart are some of the notable start-ups. The state actively facilitates and nourishes entrepreneurship to young, ambitious entrepreneurs by creating a viable ecosystem to boost start-up culture.

2.2 THE START-UP GAME

2.2.1 What is a start-up

Currently, a clear definition of a start-up does not exist. This is due to the subjective nature of innovation, ideas, businesses and complexity involved. However, there are common characteristics in the start-up definitions, i.e. scalability, technology-driven, problem-solving and initial temporary stage. Hence, a start-up can be defined as a young, dynamic company built on technology and innovation. The founders attempt to capitalise on developing a product or service to believe there is a demand.

2.2.2 Popular definitions of start-ups

Some experts defined start-ups in their terms, as follows:

According to Steve Blank, a start-up is a "temporary organisation designed to search for a repeatable and scalable business model". In contrast, a small business runs according to the fixed business model.

Paul Graham explains, "A start-up is a company designed to scale very quickly. It is this focus on growth unconstrained by geography which differentiates start-ups from small businesses. A restaurant in one town is not a start-up, nor is a franchise of start-up".

Alex Wilhelm sets his own 50-100-500 rule. According to his rule, if a company fits or exceeds any of these criteria, it is no longer a start-up.

1. \$50 million revenue run rate
2. 100 or more employees
3. Worth more than \$500 Million

2.2.3 Stages of start-up

There is no exact or universal classification of start-up phases. Hence, there is much scattered information and definitions across various sources and from different entrepreneurs. This lack of universalised approach to defining start-up stages is because the stages of start-up development are as volatile as start-ups themselves. However, in general, the stages of a start-up are classed into four broad stages:

1. Ideation/Discovery: Identify a potential scalable product or service idea for a big enough target market.
2. Validation: The service or product discovered hits the market, looking for the first clients ready to pay for it.
3. Early Traction/Maintenance: Maximising benefits and facing problems derived from the global dimension that the business has achieved
4. Scaling/Renewal: The decision to sell the start-up to a giant or acquire enormous resources that the brand will need to continue growing.

2.2.4 Start-up: Sectors

There is no exact or universal classification of start-up phases. Hence, there is much scattered information and definitions across various sources and from different entrepreneurs. This lack of universalised approach to defining start-up stages is because the stages of start-up development are as volatile as start-ups themselves. However, in general, the stages of a start-up are classed into four broad stages:

■ Deep Tech¹

A tech start-up is a company whose purpose is to bring technology products or services to market. These companies deliver new technology products or services or provide existing technology products or services in new ways.

Some prominent deep tech start-ups are DataCrux Insights and Exxar.

¹ Founders club

■ Agriculture

Crop yields remain low in India. However, the situation is slowly changing due to innovation and the use of technology in farming. An agricultural start-ups is expected to help in bettering crop yields in the near future.

Some prominent agriculture start-ups are NinjaCart, AgroStart, Gramcover, Stellapps.

■ Healthcare

Healthcare industry in India is said to be one of the fastest-growing sectors backed by India's rising income, health awareness, and access to insurance.

Some prominent healthcare start-ups are NetMeds.com, 1 mg, Portea medical and Practo.

■ Education

India's ever-growing social aspirations are helping experience rapid growth in the online education market; this sector has also received high foreign direct investment. This start-up sector has the following opportunities: Strong test preparation platforms, Platforms to reduce friction between opportunities and suitable candidates.

Prominent educational start-ups are Byjus, Toppr, Unacademy, Simplilearn.

■ Retail

Smartphones and internet penetration is taking place across the country; hence, there is a requirement of supply chain efficiency and technology innovations around engagement and personalisation. This sector can open opportunities for technology-driven operations for small stores, good connectivity and accessibility, new B2B models in retails.

Prominent start-ups in the retail sector are Flipkart, Pepperfry, Udaan, Nykaa.

■ Food

Increased urbanisation, increased disposable income levels, a rising standard of living, changing lifestyles and food habits have led to many start-ups in this sector.

Prominent start-ups in the food sector are Swiggy, Zomato, Licious, Bira, Chaipoint.

■ Banking & Financial Services

Major drivers that opened this sector to new start-ups are robust government and monetary policies, innovative banking models, the surge in domestic consumption and dynamic customer expectations. India ranks 5th in the countries with the highest non-performing assets. Initiatives like GST, Aadhar's, UPI and digitisation gave scope to many banking start-ups.

Prominent start-ups in the banking and financial sector are Paytm, Lendingkart, bankbazar.com.

■ Insurance

The low insurance density in India means massive growth opportunities in this sector. The existing shallow penetration in this sector offers significant expansion possibility.

Prominent start-ups in the Insurance sector are policybazaar.com, coverfox.com, RenewBuy.

- **Media & Entertainment**

The major drivers in this sector are massive growth in the internet and smartphones, new digital platforms, personalisation and hyper localisation, content integration with lifestyle, and reduced content creation costs.

Prominent start-ups in the media and entertainment sector are BookMyShow, Hotstar, dream11, sharechat, culturemachine.

- **Logistics**

There is a growing demand for e-commerce, automation and logistic infrastructure. Hence, the scope of this sector is in a rising trend.

Prominent start-ups in the Logistics sector are Ola, Blackbuck, Shadowfacts, Leap, Rivigo.

2.2.5 'Start-Up India': An Introduction

Across the world, start-ups are gaining importance in the 21st century. In India, in (Grant Thornton, 2016) the '70s and 80's manufacturing start-ups have been dominant. Support for the start-ups came through 'Seed Capital' and 'Soft Loans' by the Development Financial Institutions (DFI) both from the central and state levels. Some of the big names beneficiaries of this ecosystem are Reliance, Biocon, Infosys. DFI's model, however, was not sustainable. They did not make any significant gains on successful companies and lost money on failed ventures. As a result, the start-up ecosystem track was lost due to the DFI's downfall and economic liberalisation since the mid-'90s.

With the launch of the programme 'Start-up India', there is a revolution and accelerated start-up growth in India. There is a rebirth of the start-up ecosystem with more sustainable business models and supporting venture capital in the past decade. Cities such as Bangalore, Hyderabad, Chennai, Pune and Delhi are emerging as solid centres for Tech area start-ups. Start-ups have a big hand in India's economic future as it promises to bring dynamism, new thinking, and job creation.

However, the more significant problems plaguing the start-up ecosystem are the unorganised and fragmented Indian market, lack of clear and transparent policy initiatives, lack of infrastructure, lack of knowledge and exposure, and business complications. Therefore, there is a need for government, corporate, educational institutes, and other stakeholders to synergise in building a better start-up ecosystem.

2.2.6 Three Important policy Initiatives

The government has played a significant role in building a start-up ecosystem that promotes business, entrepreneurship with appropriate support. The major initiatives are:

Make in India

In September 2014, the Make in India initiative; sought to promote the manufacturing sector by encouraging companies to invest. This initiative attracted FDI and Domestic Private Investment in the growth of the manufacturing industry.

- **Start-up India**

The government has aimed to make the country a start-up destination. In August 2015, the government announced a new campaign Start-up India which would help and encourage

young Indians into entrepreneurship and innovation. This initiative made bank funding easier for start-ups. The campaign also gave a unique lead to women, tribal and dalit founders (Start-up India, 2020).

- **Digital India**

This initiative by the Indian government was to ensure that government services are more accessible and available to every citizen through an online platform. In July 2015, this initiative was announced, which translated into a massive opportunity for start-ups and e-commerce companies.

- **Financial assistance**

Since the 2015-2016 Union budget, there has been a special allocation on ecosystem building. For example, MUDRA Bank is a designated micro unit's development refinance agency to boost small business and manufacturing units by providing credit facilities. Additionally, the government has set a target to offer loans to promote new entrepreneurs and fund businesses by linking banks. Furthermore, the India allocation fund has been announced as part of the union budget to encourage a start-up ecosystem.

- **Start-up exchange**

SEBI listed new norms for a start-up, such as e-commerce ventures, which raise funding by listing on the stock exchange. This norm will provide relaxation in disclosure related requirements, takeovers and alternative investment fund regulation for start-ups.

2.2.7 Start-up Incubators

Start-up incubators assist new start-ups in their initial development phase by providing services such as infrastructural resources, office space, legal services, financial services, networking assistance, computing services and accounting services. A growing number of educational institutes have started setting up incubator programs independently or jointly. For example, Sri Ram College of Commerce, New Delhi, has set a private incubator to help their college students to build their start-ups. There are also joint incubators such as T-Hub, which has both government and personal stakeholders. There are also pure government incubators to support start-ups.

Incubators vary based on their sector focus; some incubators are solely dedicated to deep technology, while some incubate only Pharma start-ups. Some incubators are other sector-specific, and some have no sector-specific.

The count of incubators in India as of February 2021 is 696.

2.2.8 State-wise Ranking of start-ups in India

India has 3rd largest start-up ecosystem in the world. The start-ups are expected to contribute annual growth of up to 15%. India has about 1,23,781 start-ups as of February 2021. One thousand three hundred new technology start-ups were born in 2019 alone, implying about 2-3 start-ups born each day. Start-ups in the country are creating an estimation of 40,000 new jobs each year. Bangalore ranks the world's 20 leading start-ups in the 2019 Start-up Genome Project Ranking.

Map Data: © OSM - Created with Datawrapper

The above map shows the state-wise distribution of start-ups in India, recorded from the Start-up India website.

Maharashtra ranks 1st among India's states with 21,929 start-ups, followed by Karnataka, Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat and Tamil Nadu. Telangana state stands in the 7th position with 6,058 start-ups.

As observed in the above map, there is a higher concentration of start-ups in Southern India than in Northern India. North East India has the lowest share of total start-ups.

Department for Promotion of Innovation and Internal Trade

The 'Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade' (DPIIT) is a central government department under the Ministry of Commerce and Industry in India. DPIIT is responsible for formulating and implementing promotional and developmental measures for the industrial sector's growth, keeping in view the national priorities and socio-economic objectives.

For DPIIT to recognise a start-up, it requires an Industrial License. To get Industrial License, the start-up has to go through the following steps.

- The Applications go through scrutiny for their completeness.
- Once the applications for grant of license are complete with all necessary documents, DPIIT circulates them to concerned administrative ministries, Ministry of Home Affairs, Concerned State Government, and other concerned agencies for their comments.

The document for this process is as follows:

1. Create a profile on the Startup India website
 2. Give the Entity Details
 3. Furnish the Office Address
 4. Enter the Information of Authorized Representative
 5. Provide the details of Directors and Partners
 6. Record the personnel information in terms of the number of employees and other information regarding start-up.
 7. Mention any recognition or awards received by the start-up in India.
- After comments from the concerned Ministries/Agencies, files are processed and submitted to the Licensing Committee for consideration; the Licensing Committee can recommend granting license/rejection of the proposal.

Benefits of DPIIT recognition for a start-up

1. Tax exemption: After getting approved, the Start-Up can avail tax holiday/exemption for three consecutive financial years out of its first ten years since incorporation
2. Self-certification: For labour laws, the DPIIT will conduct no inspections for five years.
3. Patents
4. Easy Public Procurement Norms: Start-ups can list their product on Government e-Marketplace. Government e-Marketplace (GeM) is an online procurement platform.

Map Data: © OSM - Created with Datawrapper

The above map depicts the state-wise distribution of the start-ups recognised by DPIIT.

- The above map shows the state-wise distribution of DPIIT recognised start-ups in India. In India total number of DPIIT recognised start-ups are 41,720.
- Maharashtra has 7830 start-ups, ranking highest in the country, followed by Karnataka, Delhi. The northeast states have the least recognised start-ups in the country.
- Telangana state has 2,294 recognised start-ups in total, ranking 7th in India
- As indicated in the map, start-ups in India are not evenly distributed; there is a greater concentration of start-ups in few metropolitan cities such as Mumbai, Delhi, Hyderabad, Bangalore, Chennai and Pune.

SECTION - 3

3.1 HYDERABAD'S INTERNATIONAL TRADE IN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

The Information Technology (I.T.) sector is well defined, with international classifications comprising I.T. goods and I.T. services. The Trade-in I.T. sector has increased by leaps and bounds over the years and provides critical information and analysis of the information economy. International trade in information technology is significant to any country's development for reasons such as the following:

- It leads to value creation
- Creates employment opportunities
- Generates foreign exchange.

This section attempts to document the history of International trade in Information technology goods and services and Hyderabad's position in the global scenario by combining data from myriad sources, including the World Bank, United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), Reserve Bank of India (RBI), and official data and reports from various government departments in India.

3.1.1 The development of International Trade in Information Technology:

In 1947, Bell Labs constructed the first-ever known semiconductor transistor. It is acknowledged by many as the beginning of the contemporary information economy. The transistors were an essential component in the inventions of mainframe computers, whose commercialisation began in the 1950s and spread to most parts of the world by the 1980s. Next came Jack Kilby's integrated circuit in 1958 and later Robert Noyce in 1959. After that, integrated circuits gave rise to microprocessors/logic chips. In 1968, Gordon Moore and Robert Noyce founded Intel Cooperation to speed up microchips' commercialisation. It was preceded by the invention of Personal Computers (P.C.) by IBM, and finally, Internet adoption began in the 1990s leading to the Information revolution.

Information Technology Artifacts	Time Period
Mainframe Computers	1940s -1950s
Transistors	1940s -1950s
Programming Languages	1950s -1960s
Integrated Circuits and Chips	1960s
Online Systems	1960s
Minicomputers	1960s -1970s
Bank ATMS	1970s
Intel Microprocessor	1970s
Personal Computers	1970s -1980s
Compact Discs	1980s
Video Games	1980s
Microsoft Windows	1980s
World Wide Web	1990s
Cell Phones	1990s
DVDs	1990s
Mp3s / Phones / Tablets	2000s

Table-1: The above table shows the period for broad adoption and deployment of various technology artifacts (hardware and software)

Various factors contributed to the proliferation and diffusion of Information Technology around the world. The Cold War served as an important engine for innovation, exposure, and deployment of technology, especially in countries such as the former USSR, Great Britain, France, Australia, and the greatest extent, the U.S. from the 1940s to 1950s. It is not to say that countries witnessed the invention of technology only for military reasons. For instance, consumer electronics, including cell phones, spread rapidly across Western Europe, into Japan and South Korea.

International cooperation has also played a significant role in spreading technology and influencing various governments and national policies to allow free trade in technology worldwide. Vendors such as IBM, Phillips, Exxon, Toyota, and others exported their technologies and contributed to technology transfer in many developing countries. IBM was particularly a crucial vendor that introduced large mainframe systems to many governments, universities, and private corporations (Cortada, 2012).

Lastly, international institutions such as the World Bank, United Nations and World Trade Organization (WTO) significantly contributed to the vision of liberal and free trade in information technology. The world bank, through information technology, aimed to raise the standard of living in many developing countries, as seen in their work in Latin America, Asian and African nations, particularly in the 1970s. The Information Technology Agreement (ITA) of the WTO was another milestone that worked against free trade barriers in the I.T. Industry. The ITA was signed in 1996 and went into effect in 1997. The ITA agreement's main objective is to eliminate duties and non-tariff barriers, promote greater market access, reduce transaction costs, and enhance software export revenues. Initially, 29 participants had signed the agreement in 1996. Since then, the number of participants has grown to 82, representing about 97 per cent of world trade in I.T. products. (WTO , 1996)

Literature on economic development will show that I.T. Industry has been crucial to the growth of many economies, for instance –Great Britain in 1950s- 1960s, France in 1960s- 1970s, Japan and Korea in 1970s- 1980s and India in the 1990s – 2000s saw a surge in development with the success of their I.T. Industry.

The data available in the World Bank Database is widely considered to be the most consistent and reliable. The database has records for trade-in I.T. service exports that goes back to the 1960s. It reveals that the I.T. service trade started in 1960 with Israel taking the lead, followed by the US,

Sweden and North America in 1970, Chile in 1975, Cyprus, Korea and Sweden in 1976, and Switzerland and Algeria in 1977. These were some of the early starters of exports in Information technology services. However, it is to be pointed out that there is a shortage of data to recreate the software industry's accurate history between the 1950s- 1980s.

In the contemporary economy, studying the trade-in I.T. service exports has become extremely important because, for many countries, I.T. service exports form a considerable chunk of the revenue they receive from their I.T. industry. For example, the top 5 exporters of I.T. services in 2017 were Ireland, India, Finland, Israel and Sweden. Among them, the top 4, for instance, Ireland, India, Finland, and Israel, have more than 25 per cent of their total exports as I.T. service exports (UNCTAD, 2019).

Figure 1: Countries with Major Share of IT Exports, UNCTAD

Data from UNCTAD also reveals that the Top 10 exporters in information and technology goods accounted for 99.6% of the total value of I.T. goods exports in 2017. In the trade of I.T. goods, China ranked as the largest exporter, contributing 38% of all I.T. goods exports. Meanwhile, the Republic of Korea has shown the highest annual growth rate due mainly to I.T.'s unprecedented growth in the IoT (Internet of Things) since 2015. According to figures released by UNCTAD, the demand for electronic components used in IoT drove the trade in international imports of information and communications technology goods in 2017 to reach \$201 trillion.

Meanwhile, United States has not seen any significant growth in exports, but they remain as the top importer of I.T. goods. The U.S. is followed closely by China and Hong Kong in terms of the highest imports in I.T. goods. India has not made its place among the top countries dealing with information and technology goods.

Figure 2 & 3 : Geographical Distribution of I.T. Goods, 2017 (Imports and Exports)

As seen in the above figures, China plays a very active and prominent role in the trade of Information and Technology goods. Similarly, we know the presence of many other Asian countries. India can tap into its manufacturing Industry and compete with the top players in the trade of I.T. goods. India needs to use its strengths to its advantage to bolster its economic growth. However, from the figures given above, we can also see that economies specialise in the trade of a range of different I.T. goods and services that have helped them boost their economic development to varying periods.

As such, India specialises in the export of I.T. and I.T. enabled services. So, let us look have a look at where India stands in the trade of Information Technology.

3.1.2 Development of International Trade in Information Technology - India and Hyderabad

Jawaharlal Nehru had a vision for India. He wanted to plant the seeds for the impetus of Science and Technology in Independent India, so he presented the Scientific Policy Resolution in the Lok Sabha on March 13, 1958. He believed that "An early and large-scale development of science and technology in the country could greatly reduce the drain on capital during the early and critical stages of industrialisation."

Still, it took until 1963 for India to set up Its Electronics Committee, also known popularly as the Bhabha Committee. The Bhabha Committee was an important milestone because they came up with a report that laid out a blueprint for developing an indigenous electronics industry based on research and development, design, training and select foreign inputs. Computers' need was foreseen by information for applications in copious fields ranging from academic research to

defence and services. The report also made a strong case for the development of the Electronics Industry. It reported that the Industry could lead to the creation of up to 4 lakh jobs. All recommendations were accepted, and in 1970, a National Conference on Electronics was organised to review the electronics industry's status. The Conference made a series of recommendations. Soon enough, there was a growing realisation that self-reliance in electronics and computers- from design to development was unrealistic, and India was left behind in the race of technology. With this realisation, recommendations were made that there should be a liberal policy that would open doors for foreign collaborations in R&D and permit the import of technology to restricted organisations having strong R&D groups." The conference led to the establishment of the Department of Electronics (DoE) and the Electronics Commission (E.C.). The broad agenda of E.C. and DoE was to make India self-reliant in electronics, including computer technology. In their first annual report, the E.C. set the plan for self-reliance in computers and allowed foreign collaborations for 100% export-oriented ventures. Computers, other than those made locally, were regarded as expensive Items of imports.

The political climate was of the view that automation would lead to the loss of jobs. Thus, importing a computer would mean going through a rigorous and exhausting system to obtain clearance. Then came the era of socialist policies from 1966 to 1977. India's socialist policies were a cause of why India missed the hardware bus in the 1970s. Restrictions on importing computers and software grew, along with a priority to public sector companies such as ECIL, thus stifling the private sector. While India rejected American Majors' applications to set up manufacturing units, Hong Kong, Taiwan, Singapore, Malaysia was formulating aggressive policies to facilitate foreign investment in high technology manufacturing. The emphasis was on regulation rather than on development. By the time the DoE was ready to let Indians have minicomputers, the world had moved to microcomputers.

Indian Software Exports

Year	Net Exports (\$ million)
1980	1.4
1981	2.4
1982	4.7
1983	6.4
1984	8.9
1985	9.7
1986	13.6
1987	18.9
1988 - 1989	24.4
1989 - 1990	36.9
1990 - 1991	45.9
1991 - 1992	60.9
1992 - 1993	79.9
1993 - 1994	109.9
1994 - 1995	168.3

Table 1: India's Software Exports 1980 -1995, Source: Heeks, UNCTAD

In 1979, the Sondhi Panel proposed a rational framework for the growth of India's Information and Technology sector. The framework enabled the birth of the Indian software industry and helped many small software firms take up export jobs. For speedy approvals of manufacturing and imports, the Electronic Approval Body (EBA) was suggested to act as a single-window clearance authority for electronics. However, restrictions on importing computers and software continued, along with a priority to public sector companies such as ECIL, thus stifling the private sector yet again. A new policy on electronics was announced in 1980 which stated that the government would freely allow technology import. In 1982, DoE had begun work on a new computer policy. The policy's primary objective was to 'simplify existing procedures to enable users to obtain their requirements from indigenous sources or overseas sources, mainly regulated through fiscal measures. The policy also recognised software development as an 'industry'.

Within a year of the new computer policy, computer production grew by 100 per cent in unit terms and 65 per cent in monetary terms, while prices fell by 50 per cent. India's software exports were estimated at \$30 million in 1985, with CMC, TCS, and TBL being significant contributors. The DoE came up with a 'Policy on computer software exports development and training which aimed to promote software exports and capture a sizeable share in the international software market. This liberalisation had a mixed impact. Several thousand P.C.s came into the country and gave rise to software companies that catered to computer owners' software needs. However, the flood of foreign collaborations meant the end of R&D in Indian Companies and local firms were forced to opt for foreign cooperation in joint ventures or reselling arrangement with multinationals. (Sharma, 2009)

I.T. goods imports (% of total goods imports)

Definition: Information and communication technology goods imports include computers and peripheral equipment, communication equipment, consumer electronic equipment, electronic components, and other information and technology goods (miscellaneous).

Figure 4: Export of I.T. Goods (India) | Source: World Bank Data

I.T. services exports (% of service exports, BoP)

Definition: Information and communication technology service exports include computer and communications services (telecommunications and postal and courier services) and information services (computer data and news-related service transactions).

Figure 5: India's service exports, (% of Service Exports, BoP) | Source: World Bank Data

The ratio of computer hardware imports to exports of computer services, which was falling before the 2008 financial crisis, has since shown signs of rising. While exports of I.T. goods have remained somewhat stagnant over the years, imports in I.T. goods have surged, especially after the mobile telephone boom.

In 2016, 57 per cent of India's total exports of services were digitally delivered. Computer services were the most significant contributor, representing two-thirds of the total amount (UNCTAD, 2019). I.T. service exports have consistently bagged nearly 50 per cent of total service exports in India. USA and Canada have had the largest share of I.T. service imports from India over the years, followed by Europe, Asia, Australia and New Zealand.

Among the reasons that India's I.T. Industry took off, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is a critical component. FDI inflows come through foreign affiliates, cross-border Mergers and Acquisitions (M&A), exports, Transnational companies (TNCs) and R&D projects. The key sectors that attract maximum FDI inflows in India include the service segment, computer software and hardware, telecommunications, construction development, automobile, chemicals, and pharmaceuticals.

Figure 5 and Table 3 below indicate the country-wise distribution of India's software service and India's total FDI equity inflow in the computer and hardware sector, respectively.

COUNTRY WISE DISTRIBUTION OF SOFTWARE SERVICE EXPORTS

Figure 6: Geographical Distribution of India's Software Service Exports, (RBI, 2020)

Between January 2000 and September 2019, FDI Inflows in India's computer software Industry have soared, while the hardware sector is still struggling to attract FDI.

Sub Sectors	FDI equity Inflows (Rs crore)	% with total FDI Inflows
Computer Software Industry	261,985.95	9.37
Computer Hardware	3,158.59	0.11
Others (Software)	1,345.62	0.05
Total of above	266,490.16	9.53

Table 3: FDI Inflows in Computer and Hardware Sector, Source: (DPIIT, 2019)

In this period, the table indicates that nearly 99 per cent of India's FDI equity inflows go to India's computer and hardware sector. Mauritius ranked first in the top five countries' share, attracting FDI equity inflows into India's computer and hardware sector, sending across 29% of FDI. It was followed by Singapore (26%), the USA (13%), Netherlands (10%) and the Cayman Islands (5%).

Further, FDI data for the same period (2000-2019) shows the share of states in India that attracted the highest FDI equity inflows.

RBI's Regional Office	States Covered	Amount of FDI Equity Inflows (Rs. crore)	% with Total FDI Inflows
■ Bangalore	Karnataka	66,565.19	25.18
■ New Delhi	Delhi, Part of UP and Haryana	60,025.27	23.14
■ Mumbai	Maharashtra, Dadra Nagar Haveli, Daman and Diu	56,008.19	22.30
■ Chennai	Tamil Nadu, Pondicherry	11,279.15	5.02
■ Hyderabad	Andhra Pradesh	10,977.08	4.25
Total		204,854.88	79.89

Table 4: State Wise Share of FDI Equity Inflows in Computer and Hardware Sector between 2000-2019 (DPIIT, 2019)

As seen from above, Bangalore has received the highest share of FDI equity inflows between 2000-2019, followed by New Delhi, Mumbai, Chennai, and Hyderabad. Hyderabad ranks 5th In India with a total share of 4.45% of the total percentage of FDI equity inflows in India's computer and hardware sector.

However, Hyderabad has seen a consistent rise in its share of growth in the Information Technology sector. In the financial year 2019-2020, Hyderabad saw an overall percentage of 23.5 per cent in India's I.T. export growth. Telangana's share of India's I.T. exports for the year 2019-2020 was 11.6%. Hyderabad has seen a growth rate of more than 100 per cent between the year 2014 to 2020. Its exports in the I.T. sector have doubled over the period.

Figure 7 : I.T./ITeS Exports, Telangana

Source: (Electronics and Communication Department, Telangana, 2020).

Telangana's I.T. sector is led by I.T. and ITeS companies set up in Hyderabad in the 1990s. (ITeS refers to Information Technology Enabled service. It includes a large variety of operations dependent on I.T. to enhance an organisation's efficiency.) According to data collected by Software Technology Park of India (STPI), In the Financial Year (F.Y.) 2000-2001, Andhra Pradesh's contribution to India's I.T. exports stood around 10 per cent with a value of 2017 cr. However, currently, Hyderabad has achieved a growth rate of 17.93% from the F.Y. 2018-2019 to F.Y. 2019-2020. Increasingly, Hyderabad is becoming a hub for entrepreneurs and I.T./ITeS companies.

London and Partners (L&P), an International Trade, Investment and promotion agency, analysed the top 20 global cities that successfully attracted foreign direct investment (FDI) into information and communications technology. Hyderabad ranked 14th in attracting FDI in ICT and Electronics sector, with 20 companies investing in 2018.

There are several reasons why large multinational companies choose Hyderabad and see its potential as a technology giant. The world's top five majors have chosen Hyderabad to establish their facilities. With the constant support of its state government, Hyderabad has become the hub for global I.T. majors and is gradually replacing Bangalore as the I.T. capital of India.

CONCLUSION

Delving into data and learning of the I.T. trajectory of Hyderabad from multiple perspectives as this paper does, contrasts the city's success with I.T. and areas where it needs to improve. Each of these perspectives is directly or indirectly a part of the puzzle of Hyderabad's status as an I.T. Hub.

On the beauraucratic front, what was done in the past has done wonders in creating a strong foundation for the I.T. Industry to take off. Entrepreneurs say that further toning down of bureaucratic hurdles needs to be done in line with other international practices. Furthermore, both Industry leaders and academia agree that education and skilling of new workers from academia is and would be a big challenge that needs to be aptly resolved. Unless this is addressed, the opinion is that the city will not significantly grow up the value chain of I.T. services.

Coming to the start-up scenario, there is a suitable environment for the initial stages of starting up of companies. But there is a severe lack of an environment after the initial validation of the business Ideas. Startup's from Hyderabad have typically either been bought out or merged into other businesses. There are hardly any unicorns from Hyderabad for its size and the amount of business that is conducted here.

Finally, international trade in I.T. services has come a long way from where it started. It is to be noted that to improve international trade in I.T., expansion of the Industry's offerings would not be enough. The existing services that Hyderabad's I.T. provides need to be re-envisioned. The Industry needs to grow out of being a master back-office services hub to that of an innovation centre. Proactive Steps need to be taken in education and reimagined governance to achieve this sustainedly.

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3. Neelima Khetan headed the CSR division for companies like Coca-Cola, the Vedanta Group and Hindustan Zinc Limited. She is now visiting fellow at Brookings India
4. Amitabh Kundu has been chairperson of the Post-Sachar Evaluation Committee set up by Ministry of Minority Affairs. Currently, he is chairs a Committee for Swachh Bharat Mission at the Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation.
5. Aalok Wadhwa is a management professional with more than three decades of experience working in FMCG, online and social media content, publishing, and retail businesses.
6. Saleema Razvi is a Research Economist at the Copenhagen Consensus Center. She has previously served in organisations like Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations, Population Foundation of India, and UNICEF.
7. Abdul Shaban is a Professor at Tata Institute of Social Sciences. He has been a member of Post-Sachar Evaluation Committee, Chief Minister's High-Powered Committee on Muslims, Government of Maharashtra; and Sudhir Commission, Telangana.
8. Adeeluddin Syed is a Director at CDPP, and a philanthropist and social worker.
9. Jeemol Unni is a former Director of the Institute of Rural Management, Anand (IRMA) and RBI Chair Professor of Economics at IRMA. She is currently Professor at Ahmedabad University.

CDPP - RESEARCH TEAM

1. G. Sudhir is Chairman of the Research Team at CDPP, and a former IAS officer.
2. Amir Ullah Khan, Research Director at CDPP, is a former Civil Servant. He has worked with Encyclopedia Britannica, India Development Foundation and the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation.
3. Netheena Mathews, Senior Fellow (Publications), is also the Managing Editor of the Journal of Development Policy and Practice. She has past experience in Policy Research and Advocacy, Journalism and Academic Publishing.
4. Nahia Hussain, Vice President (Policy Affairs) at CDPP, has worked on diverse issues like Gender Rights, Sustainability, Foreign Policy, and Criminal Justice.
5. Sriram Bhupathiraju, Analyst at CDPP, is an anthropologist with an MPhil from IIT, Hyderabad.
6. Anjana Divakar is Research Associate at CDPP with a Master's in Public Policy from Jindal School of Government and Public Policy. She is Managing Editor of the Journal of Development Policy and Practice.
7. Samia Farheen is research intern at CDPP. She has a triple major in Psychology, Economics and Sociology from Mount Carmel College, Bangalore.
8. Syed Salman Uddin is research assistant at CDPP. He has a degree in mechanical engineering from JNTU.
9. Syed Moin Afroz is Lead Graphic Designer at CDPP. He has been a part of the design industry for a decade now.
10. Ismail Shaikh is an Editorial and Communications intern at CDPP.

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